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CHICKEN FEATHER AS A SUBSTITUTE OF FINE AGGREGATE IN MORTAR

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Abstract:

An experimental investigation aimed to determine the viability of chicken feathers as substitute for fine aggregates for concrete was conducted. Chicken feathers collected from slaughter houses (waste material) were utilized after previous studies conducted revealed that chicken feathers possess good durability and resistance to degradation because of the extensive cross-linking and strong covalent bonding within its structure. In the investigation conducted, the chicken feathers content ranged from 1% to 7% of the total volume of fine aggregates. The aggregate-cement ratio was 1:6 and 1:3 cement was held constant with varying water-cement ratio in every mixture. Specimens were grouped according to their number of days of curing as follows; 3, 7 and 14, days. The results affirmed that the compressive strengths of the specimens are inversely proportional to the level of feathers that were added. The specimen with 3% feathers, cured in 14 days, yielded a compressive strength of 16.61 Mpa. This value met the Type S mortar cement of ASTM C270-91 standard specification that covers mortars for use in the construction of non-reinforced and reinforced unit structures. Mix workability decreased significantly as the proportion by weight of feathers or ground feathers increased from 1% to 7%. Stiffness, flexural strength, and dimensional stability of the feather-cement boards decreased as the proportion of feathers was increased above 3%. Higher proportions of feather, however, showed significant reduction in modulus of elasticity (MOE) and modulus of rupture (MOR), and increased water absorption and thickness swelling after 24 hours of soaking in water.

Key Words: Chicken Feather, Portland Cement, Keratin, Curing, Workability, Compressive Strength

INTRODUCTION

An estimated 15 million tons of chicken feathers are available worldwide each year as a by-product of meat manufacture. Currently the feathers are disposed of in landfill, burned or processed to make a low-grade animal feedstock but these methods are environmentally unsafe. Feathers are made from protein keratin there are two forms of microcrystalline keratin in the feathers, just as WOOL, but the surface area is much larger because the diameter of the fiber is much smaller. So the fiber can absorb more water than the wool or cellulose fibers. Based on these, efforts have been made to utilize them and to produce a nonwoven web.

Protein waste has evoked the interest of scientists for many years. The material is attractive not only for uses in medicine and biotechnology, but also as a component of barrier materials. One of the least investigated and still not exploited protein waste materials is keratin-rich (Ca: 95%) chicken feathers. However due to its availability, abundance and properties, it has gained popularity as a potential component of composites combined with other biopolymers. Development created a way for the use of chicken feather fibre as reinforcement in composite products. A simple, practical way to include poultry feather into composite boards is to bind them with Portland cement.

Simplified studies on this aspect of feather utilization have been reported. However, if this could be proven possible, it could offer an affordable new building material with both economic and environmental advantages. The feathers consist of three basic sections, as depicted in Figure 1: the quill, the pennaceous fibers, which are located on the upper portion of the quill, and the plumulaceous fibers, which extend from the lower part of the quill. The plumulaceous fibers usually consist of a stem with two to three branches attached, and are soft and flexible. The pennaceous fibers are generally straighter, stiffer, and larger in diameter than the plumulaceous fibers.

In keratin protein there are both hydrophilic and hydrophobic amino acids, but 39 of the 95 amino acids are hydrophilic. The action of acids, alkalis and solvents on feather fibers were found by a solubility test. The visible change in fibers due to chemical action was observed.

- **Effect of Acids** : The feathers have good chemical resistance to mild acids, but have poor resistance to strong acids, so they get dissolved.
- **Effect of Alkalies** : The feathers have good chemical resistance to mild acids, but have poor resistance to strong acids, so they get dissolved. The chicken feather fibers degrade rapidly in alkali environments, but significantly less in near-neutral and slightly acidic conditions.

The functions of a bird's feathers are highly related to their mechanical properties and their mechanical properties are related to the keratin structure. Keratin has a structure which transports forces through negligible distortion. It is reported that elasticity modulus of feather keratin ranges from 0.045 GPa to 10 GPa. The Young's modulus of chicken feather fibers was found to be in the range of 3 - 50 GPa and the tensile strength of oven-dried chicken feather fibers in the range of 41-130 Mpa

METHODOLOGY

Preparation of Chicken Feathers

Purified and screened fibres were washed three times in water at about 40 °C with a detergent for 1 hr. and then centrifuged for 10 min. after this process feathers were left in direct contact to the sunlight. After this we get a fine looking fibre which is now ready to be used.

The purified fibres were disintegrated by

- Cutting using a paper cutter
- Using scissors.

Fig No. 1: Chicken Feathers after washing

Binders

Ordinary Portland cement was used as the mixture binding material. The cement used in the study is a Type 1P. This type of cement is an intimate and uniform blend of portland cement or portland blast-furnace slag cement and fine pozzolan produced either by inter grinding portland cement clinker and pozzolan or by blending portland cement or portland blast-furnace slag cement and finely divided pozzolan in which the pozzolan constituent is between 15 and 40 percent by weight of the portland-pozzolan-cement.

"Cement consumption is increasing globally by 5% per year" both now and in the future. Although there are several different types of cement, portland cement PC is the most widely used and for simplicity"

Fig No. 2: Ordinary Portland Cement Used For Making Samples

Cement-Aggregate Ratio

The cement-aggregate ratio of the mix is 1:6 and 1:3. The volume of cement is held constant in all mixtures at different levels of feather-aggregate ratio. With the presence of feathers that gradually replaced fine aggregates, the resulting volume of the mixtures increased because the specific weight of feathers is lower compared to that of fine aggregates.

According to Merrit (1976), "Cement served as the binder of the aggregates, and with cement content increasing, the strength is also increasing". Thus, the resulting compressive strength gradually decreases as the feather level increases unless the quantity of cement is increased. In this study the normal behavior of cement in the concrete with regards to cement-aggregate ratio is altered by the increasing presence of the quantity of feathers

Water-Cement Ratio

During the sampling procedures, it has been observed that the increase of water content in each succeeding mixtures, from 0% to 7% level of chicken feathers, is proportional to the increase of the chicken feather levels even if the quantity of fine aggregates decreases. The increase of water content in every mix, upon the addition of chicken feathers and even the decrease of fine aggregates, was due to the water absorbed by the chicken feathers and the water needed for the cement paste that could fill up the interstices between solid particles (i.e. fine aggregates and feather fibers) in the mix. It should be remembered that the absorption of chicken feather is 41.36% which is very much higher compared to the fine aggregates used which is 4.35%.

Fine Aggregate – Chicken Feathers Ratio

There were seven assortments of mixtures of specimens that were prepared. One of which was without feather content, a mixture of pure fine aggregates, cement and water only. The fine aggregates of the other six mixtures were gradually substituted by chicken feathers in different levels of percentages (i.e. 1%, 3%, 5%, and 7%). The specimens with 0% feather content have the highest compressive strengths. As the feathers replace fine aggregates in increasing manner, the compressive strength decreases. Therefore, the varying ratios of fine aggregate with respect to the chicken feathers affected the compressive strength of the specimens. It indicates that the compressive strengths of the specimens are inversely proportional to the increase of the feather levels.

The required amount of dry raw materials of the specimens was prepared, that corresponds to the volume of the batch to be mixed. All the raw materials were dry-mixed thoroughly in the mixing bowl. Then water was gradually added as mixing of the materials continued until the desired consistency was attained. The mixing of materials lasted up to more or less 5 minutes, enough for the feathers and the aggregates to absorb water.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK:

In this test 8 batches of cubes were made (i.e. 24 cubes) and they were being cured for 3 days. After three days the cubes were removed from water and the water was removed which was at the surface of the cube with the help of dry cloth, the weight of the cubes was noted down. The cubes were then installed in the oven for drying for 1 day.

Fig No. 3: Chicken Feather Cubes

TABLE 1: Composition Of Ingredients (BY WT), { USING MIX 1:6 }

Percentage of feathers	Weight of cement (in gm)	Wieght of sand (in gm)	Weight of feathers (in gm)	Weight of water (in gm)	Cement sand ratio
0 %	320	1920	171	0	1:6
3%	320	1863	186	57	1:6
5%	320	1824	200	96	1:6
7%	320	1786	215	134	1:6

TABLE 2: Composition Of Ingredients (BY WT), { USING MIX 1:3 }

Percentage of feathers	Weight of cement (in gm)	Wieght of sand (in gm)	Weight of feathers (in gm)	Weight of water (in gm)	Cement sand ratio
0 %	550	1650	0	286	1:3
3%	550	1600	50	310	1:3
5%	550	1568	82	340	1:3
7%	550	1534	116	360	1:3

TABLE 3: For Normal Mortar (Percentage of Feather - 0%)

S.N	Mortar mix ratio (1:6)				Mortar mix ratio (1:3)			
	Wet Wt	Dry wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)	Wet wt	Dry Wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)
1.	660	560	100	17.85	740	680	60	8.8
2.	640	540	100	18.5	740	690	50	7.2
3.	660	540	120	22.22	720	660	60	9.09

Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:6) = 19.5%

Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:3) = 8.36%

Fig No. 4: Water absorption for normal mortar

TABLE 4: For Mortar (Percentage of Feather - 3%)

S.N	Mortar mix ratio (1:6)				Mortar mix ratio (1:3)			
	Wet Wt	Dry wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)	Wet wt	Dry Wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)
1.	600	520	80	15.3	740	680	60	8.8
2.	620	550	70	12.7	730	660	70	10.6
3.	620	540	80	14.8	730	670	60	8.9

Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:6) = 14.2%, Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:3) = 9.43%

Fig No. 5: Water absorption for chicken feather mortar

TABLE 5: For Mortar (Percentage of Feather - 5%)

S.N.	Mortar mix ratio (1:6)				Mortar mix ratio (1:3)			
	Wet Wt	Dry wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)	Wet wt	Dry Wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)
1.	600	500	100	20	740	670	70	10.4
2.	630	520	110	21.1	730	650	80	12.3
3.	630	530	100	18.8	750	680	70	10.2

Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:6) = 19.9%

Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:3) = 15.7%

Fig No. 6: Water Absorption for Chicken Feather Mortar

TABLE 6: For Mortar (Percentage of Feather - 7%)

S.N	Mortar mix ratio (1:6)				Mortar mix ratio (1:3)			
	Wet Wt	Dry wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)	Wet wt	Dry Wt	Net Wt	Water absorption (%)
1.	630	510	120	23.5	760	650	110	16.9
2.	600	490	110	22.4	770	670	100	14.9
3.	620	480	140	29.1	750	650	100	15.3

Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:6) = 25%

Avg water absorption for mortar mix ratio (1:3) = 15.7%

Fig No. 7: Water Absorption for Chicken Feather Mortar

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST

The compression strength was obtained based on average of three cubes of size (each) 7.06 x 7.06 x 7.06 cm were prepared for each content , three of them for 3 days strength tests, three for 7 days and the other three for 14 days strength test . The samples are cubes which are recommended by ASTM for tests on mortar.

Fig No. 8: Compressive Strength Testing Machine

TABLE7: For Mortar Ratio (Cement:Sand (1: 6)) Compressive Strength , Without Chicken Feathers

Percentage Of feathers	No of days		
	3 days Strength (in mpa)	7 days Strength (in mpa)	14 days Strength (in mpa)
0%	5.2	15.2	20.7
	5.1	15.6	20.1
	5.4	15.3	21.0
	AVG=5.23	AVG=15.36	AVG=20.6

TABLE 8: For Mortar Ratio (Cement:Sand (1:3)) Compressive Strength, Without Chicken Feathers

Percentage Of feathers	No of days		
	3 days strength (in mpa)	7 days strength (in mpa)	14 days strength (in mpa)
0%	50.4	70.4	103.9
	48.9	72.3	105.1
	51.2	69.1	102.3
	AVG =50.16	AVG =7.6	AVG =103.7

TABLE 9: For Varying Chicken Feather Percentage (Ratio 1:6)

Percentage Of feathers	No of days		
	3 days strength (in mpa)	7 days strength (in mpa)	14 days strength (in mpa)
3 %	5.0	13.5	16.9
	4.7	13.9	16.4
	4.6	13.4	16.5
	AVG=4.76	AVG=13.6	AVG=16.6
5%	3.9	11.6	13.7
	4.5	11.2	13.1
	4.6	11.7	12.9
	AVG=4.33	AVG=11.5	AVG=13.23
7%	2.7	10.1	10.5
	3.1	9.7	10.6
	2.9	9.5	11.1
	AVG=2.9	AVG=9.8	AVG=10.73

TABLE 10: For Varying Chicken Feather Percentage (Ratio 1 : 3)

Percentage Of feathers	No of days		
	3 days Strength (in mpa)	7 days Strength (in mpa)	14 days Strength (in mpa)
3 %	45.3	65.0	102.3
	44.2	65.4	100.1
	45.1	64.8	98.2
	AVG =44.86	AVG =65.06	AVG =99.53
5%	40.5	60.3	91.2
	38.7	61.2	93.2
	39.6	61.6	91.9
	AVG =39.6	AVG =61.03	AVG =92.1
7%	35.1	52.0	85.4
	34.9	52.1	85.9
	36.2	51.3	84.8
	AVG =35.4	AVG =52.06	AVG =85.36

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Fig No. 9: Showing Results When Mortar Mix Proportion is 1:6

Fig No 10: Showing Results When Mortar Mix Proportion is 1:3

TESTS ON CEMENT

• **TEST FOR FINENESS**

It is done on sieve 90 micron IS sieve , a small amount of cement is taken and passed through 90micron IS sieve. the weight of retained cement is taken and fineness is calculated by dividing the retained weight to the total weight .the weight should not be more than 10%.

TABLE 11: Fineness of Cement

S.No	Wt of sample (gm) (2)	Wt of passing (3)	Col (2)- col (3) Wt of residue	Fineness= (wt of residue/wt of sample) x 100
1	100	92.7	7.3	7.3
2	100	91.8	8.3	8.3
3	100	90	10	10

Avg percentage of fineness of cement =10%

Fig No 11: Sieves Being Used For Fineness Testing

- **CONSISTENCY TEST**

TABLE 12: Consistency of Cement

S.NO.	Quantity of cement added (in gm)	% of dry wt of cement	Time of gauging (in minutes)	Penetration from bottom of mould (mm)
1	300	26.7	4.5	5.5
2	300	26.7	4.7	5.8
3	300	26.7	4.8	6

Avg of consistency test of cement=26.7%

Fig No 12: Vicat Apparatus for Consistency test.

- SETTING TIME TEST –**

Fig No 13: Vicat Apparatus for Setting Time Test

- FOR INITIAL SETTING TIME:** 300 gm of cement is taken and it is mixed with 0.85P water, P is percentage of water in consistency test.

TABLE 13: Initial Setting Time

S.No.	Time from water added(min)	Penetration from bottom (mm)
1	32	5
2	29	5
3	34	5

Avg of initial setting time of cement=31.6min

- FOR FINAL SETTING TIME:**

TABLE 14: Final Setting Time

S.NO.	Time from water added(hours)	Avg
1	9.6	10.06
2	9.54	
3	10.10	

Avg final setting time of cement=10.06hrs

- SOUNDNESS TEST:** In the soundness test a specimen of hardened cement paste is boiled for a fix time so that any tendency to expand is speeded up and can be detected and soundness means ability to resist volume expansion.

Fig No 14: Le Chateliers Apparatus for Soundness Test

TABLE 15: Soundness Test

S.No	Data required	Sample no 1	Sample no 2	Sample no 3
1.	Wt of cement sample (in gm)	100	100	100
2.	Water required for std. consistency (P) %	26.7	26.7	26.7
3.	Water added to the sample (0.78p) % (in gm)	20.8	20.8	20.8
4.	Distance between pointer ends before heating (D1)	15	18	19
5.	Time of heating (min)	30	30	30
6.	Distance between pointer ends after heating (D2)	25	26	28
7.	Difference (D2-D1)	10	8	9

Avg of soundness test of cement=9

CONCLUSION

The following result shows that the varying percentage of the chicken feather results in strength shifting of the mixture. According to the tests that were conducted on the sample shows that the strength of the sample remains stable till when the percentage of the feather is up to 5% and then the strength of sample decreases with increase in percentage. The results show that the best results can be found when the percentage of the chicken feathers is 3% and it provides the same strength as of normal mortar or concrete. The following diagram shows the samples that were made by the normal mortar (percentage of the chicken feather was 0%) and the mortar with a mix of 3% chicken feather. If we look closely in the diagram we can see the little traces of the fibres of the feathers

Consequently, boards showed improved dimensional stability at 3% to 5% feather content. At higher feather loading, the boards showed very high water absorption and thickness swelling (>5%) after 24 hours of water soaking. These boards are likely to have contained too much feather for the level of coupling agent and cement used such that fibers were not completely coated with cement

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INDIAN STANDARD CODE:

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2. IS 516:195- Methods Of Test For Strength Of Concrete.
3. IS 456:2000- Code Of Practise For Plain And Reinforced Concrete.
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